

STUDY ON TRUSS TYPE SEGMENTAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURE FOR TEMPORARY RESCUE BRIDGE

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ABSTRACT

Typhoons and earthquakes, which occur frequently in Taiwan, often lead to the washout or collapse of river bridges, thereby causing traffic interruption. The temporary rescue bridge is recognized as being considered to be the approach of disaster relieving operation, when a bridge structurally loses its workability. In this paper, a truss type segmental composite temporary rescue bridge is proposed, and a 50-m span asymmetric self-anchored truss type segmental cable-stayed bridge is designed, and experimentally validated to improve the stiffness of a longer span (50m) bridge. The proposed autonomous assembly technology for construction were validated by an on-site experiment and virtual model experiment. The assembly process had been found to improve the worker safety of the bridge construction and shorten assembly time of the bridge. Two different construction processes, the cantilever erection method and the incremental launching method, had be compared to improve the safety of the workers. The results of this study indicated that: (1) the truss type segmental composite bridge could improve the stiffness of 50-m span temporary rescue bridge to meet the requirement of deflection-to-span ratio; (2) autonomous assembly technology for bridge construction has a significant contribution to improving the worker safety and shortening assembly time of the temporary rescue bridge; (3) the incremental launching method has more operational efficiency then the cantilever erection method; (4) the incremental launching method could prevent workers from constructing above the river and should be more secure for safety.

1 INTRODUCTION

Typhoons and earthquakes, which occur frequently in Taiwan, often lead to the washout or collapse of river bridges, thereby causing traffic interruption. The temporary rescue bridge is recognized as being considered to be the approach of disaster relieving operation, when a bridge structurally loses its workability. Yeh et. al. applied glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) material in a segmental temporary rescue bridge design making it light-weight and reusable [1]. The live load capacity of the GFRP bridges was 5 tons, and the span was 20 meters. However, when taking actual working environment into consideration, the span length may be too short and the assembly of this bridge may be difficult. The reason is that not only the weather may not be suitable for construction but also it is hard to protect safety of construction workers on-site.

To clarify the main reason of these problems, we will use truss type segmental structure to improve the stiffness of a longer span (50m) bridge, and analyzed the process of constructing the GFRP temporary rescue bridge. The assembly process has been found to be so critical that it majorly controlled the construction progress and the worker safety of the bridge construction. Two different processes which are cantilever erection method and incremental launching method will be compared to improve the safety of the workers.

2 DESIGN AND EXPERIMENT OF COMPOSITE BRIDGE

2.1 Design of truss type composite bridge

The design case looked at communities that were isolated by Typhoon Morakot in 2009. A river bridge with a 50 m span length was washed away by the floods, interrupting traffic travelling to and from surrounding areas. A temporary rescue bridge needed to be completed within 8 hours, so that small trucks of 3.5 tons could access and transport relief materials into the isolated area.

This study develops such a temporary rescue bridge system by using a self-balancing approach with cantilever erection method or incremental launching method. An asymmetric self-anchored truss type segmental composite cable-stayed bridge is proposed. Truss type GFRP segmental bridge systems were studied to assess the structural requirements necessary to meet the following design requirements: 50 m span; 3 m width; 5 tons live load capability; and a deflection-to-span ratio of $L/400$, which was recommended by USDA [2]. Fig. 1(a) and Fig. 1(b) shows the design results and finite element method (FEM) model of the asymmetric self-anchored truss type segmental composite cable-stayed bridge. The main girders of the bridge system with truss type structural segments were composed of $203 \times 60 \times 9.5$ mm C-shaped and $101 \times 101 \times 6$ mm box shaped GFRP composite members. The material properties of GFRP were as follows: Young's modulus = 20.03 GPa; density = 1.72 g/cm^3 ; and allowable stress = 207 MPa. Fig. 1(c) and Fig. 1(d) shows the deformation shape and shape deformation under various loading position. The maximum displacement is 10.67 cm, which meet the design requirement for a deflection-to-span ratio of $L/400$.

(d)

Figure 1: Design results and FEM model of 50-m span temporary rescue bridge, (a) full bridge, (b) truss type girders and structural segment (unit: mm), (c) the deformation shape, (d) shape deformation (various loading position).

2.2 Experiment of truss type composite segment

As shown in Fig. 2, the specimen composed with three main girders are denoted G1, G2, and G3 and connected by three diaphragms are denoted D1, D2, and D3. Preparation of specimen for truss type segments of composite temporary rescue bridges was shown in Fig. 3. The typical experimental setup for flexural test was shown in Fig. 4. The test program included a flexural test to measurement the deformation shapes and stiffness of the truss type composite segment, in order to calibrate the FEM model.

Figure 2: Top view and side view of the test specimen (units: mm).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3: Preparation of specimens, (a) assemble of truss type main girder, (b) completion of truss type main girders, (c) completion of truss type composite segment.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Experiment setup for flexural test, (a) applied loading at 1/2 span of specimen, (b) applied loading at 1/4 span of specimen.

The specimen was first tested by flexural loadings applied at 1/2 span of specimen, followed by a flexural test applied at 1/4 span of specimen. Both tests were performed by controlling load with the design's target loading of 50 kN. Comparisons between laboratory measurements and analytical results obtained from FEM model are presented in Figs. 5-6. Fig. 5 gives the deformation shape of G2 girder at the applied load of $P = 50$ kN at the mid span. In these figure, the solid lines and dashed line denote the analytical results and experimental measurements, respectively. As shown in these figures, the FEM model can predict the GFRP bridge deflection with satisfactory accuracy. Fig. 6 gives the force-deflection curves at the mid span. In these figures, force-deflection curves denoted as stiffness of the test specimen. As shown in these figures, the finite model can predict the stiffness of the GFRP truss type composite bridge segment with satisfactory accuracy. Therefore, the FEM models are validated from the comparison of analytical results and experimental results.

Figure 5: Comparison results for the deflection of the specimen at the applied load of $P = 20-50$ kN (solid lines: analytical results; dashed lines: experimental measurements).

Figure 6: Comparison results for the force-deflection curve of the specimen at the applied load of $P = 0-50$ kN (solid lines: analytical results; dashed lines: experimental measurements).

3 AUTONOMOUS ASSEMBLY TECHNOLOGY FOR CONSTRUCTION

3.1 Development of autonomous assembly technology

In the research, we utilized the connector from previous research for autonomous beam assembly [3]. The automated beam assembly framework identified critical elements for research development and proposed a construction process providing an automated approach utilizing a mobile crane to build up a temporary rescue bridge. The critical elements were categorized into two parts: structure and automated process. The structure part, including segmental structure, light weight, and structural connector, defines the requirement of the material and structural geometry to be used in a construction. The automated process part, considers technical requirement on how a mobile crane finishes hoists and assembly tasks without any worker on site.

3.2 Experiment and results

The framework and the construction process were validated by the experiment described in this section. The proposed assembly process were validated by an on-site experiment and virtual model experiment.

The proposed assembly process were validated by an on-site experiment. The experiment measured the placement deviation from the targeted position of the hoisted structural component for assembly (Fig. 7). A crane with hydraulic retractable boom with the maximum load capacity of 3.4 tons was used in the experiment. The payload was an approximately 80kg and 1.45m beam. The crane operation was executed by a graduate student in the experiment. The student learnt crane operations from a professional crane operator, and practiced the required operation of the sway reduction before the experiment. Fig. 8 shows the on-site experiment environment and results of the automated process. The result of X deviation was 3.03cm in average, and the result of Y deviation was 1.37cm.

Figure 7: Measurement of structural component deviation from selected target.

Figure 8: On-site experiment environment and results of the automated process.

The “release the beam for assembly triggered by gravity” process were validated by a virtual model experiment. We created a virtual structural component and used a virtual mobile crane to simulate the rotation of the structural connector. The virtual model was created on a commercial physics engine, Unity3D. Fig. 9 shows the results of virtual beam assembly by a mobile crane. The virtual model successfully demonstrated the “release the beam for assembly triggered by gravity” process.

Figure 9: The results of virtual beam assembly by a mobile crane.

4 CONSTRUCTION OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS

4.1 Description of operational efficiency analysis

The operational efficiency analysis for task of disaster relief by temporary rescue bridges compare the operational efficiency indicators between the cantilever erection method (Fig. 10) and the incremental launching method (Fig. 11). The efficiency indicators are such as (1) safety of workers, (2) construction time, (3) equipment and manpower required for construction, (4) demand for counterweight, etc.

Safety of workers is the first indicator for consideration. For the cantilever erection method, a mini-crawler crane instead of workers in river-crossing process to improve the safety of the workers. Nevertheless, the incremental launching method is to carry out the assembly on the river side and then push forward to isolating end to avoid the construction process above the river to ensure workers safety.

Figure 10: Cantilever erection method for rescue bridge construction, (a) assemble segments of the weight-balance module, (b) assemble the first GFRP truss segment of crossing structural module and lifting to cross the river, (c)(d) repeat stage (b) for second to ninth GFRP truss segments, (e) completed the construction sequence to cross the river.

Figure 11: Incremental launching method for rescue bridge construction, (a) assemble segments of the weight-balance module, (b) assemble the first GFRP truss segment and install launching noise, (c) assemble the second GFRP truss segment and push it forward, (d) repeat stage (c) for third to ninth segments (e) completed the construction sequence to cross the river.

4.2 Construction time analysis

The construction time analysis for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge compare the total construction time between the original construction method without autonomous assembly technology, the cantilever erection method with autonomous assembly technology, and the incremental launching method.

Fig. 12 shows the results of construction time analysis between three different construction processes for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge. The gray line represents the original construction method, the total construction time is around 540 minutes, do not meet the requirement within 8 hours. The red line represents the cantilever erection method, owing to the helpful of autonomous assembly technology, the total construction time is shortened to 430 minutes and meet the requirement within 8 hours. The blue line represents the incremental launching method, because of avoid the construction process above the river, the total construction time is drastically shortened to 370 minutes and meet the requirement within 8 hours.

Figure 12: The results of construction time analysis between three different construction processes for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge.

4.3 Equipment and manpower analysis

The equipment and manpower analysis for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge compare the equipment and manpower between the original construction method, the cantilever erection method, and the incremental launching method. The equipment for original construction method include simple tools, and a small truck with a crane. The equipment for cantilever erection method include simple tools, a small truck with a crane, and a mini-crawler crane instead of workers in river-crossing process. The incremental launching method use the same equipment as the cantilever erection method.

Fig. 13 shows the results of manpower analysis between three different construction processes for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge. The gray line represents the original construction method, the maximum manpower is around 20 persons, and totally 30 workers are needed during whole construction time. The red line represents the cantilever erection method, the maximum manpower is around 15 persons, and totally 30 workers are needed during whole construction time. The blue line represents the incremental launching method, the maximum manpower is around 25 persons, and totally 30 workers are needed during whole construction time.

Figure 13: The results of manpower analysis between three different construction processes for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge.

4.4 Demand for additional counterweight

The truss type composite temporary rescue bridge are constructed by using a self-balancing approach with cantilever erection method or incremental launching method. Before completion of the composite bridge construction, there are additional counterweight needed for balance of mini-crawler crane and self-weight of composite segments during construction.

Fig. 14 shows the results of demand for additional counterweight between two different construction processes for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge. The red line represents the cantilever erection method, the additional counterweight is needed from 1.8 tons to 25.8 tons during river-crossing process. The blue line represents the incremental launching method, the additional counterweight is needed from 3.8 tons to 8.9 tons during river-crossing process.

Figure 14: The results of demand for additional counterweight between two different construction processes for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study indicated that: (1) the truss type segmental composite bridge could improve the stiffness of 50-m span rescue bridge to meet the requirement of deflection-to-span ratio; (2) autonomous assembly technology for bridge construction has a significant contribution to improving the worker safety and shortening assembly time of the rescue bridge; (3) the incremental launching method has more operational efficiency than the cantilever erection method; (4) the incremental launching method could prevent workers from constructing above the river and should be more secure for safety.

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